

STUDY OF MASS KINETIC OF THE HYDROLYSIS OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY (CFRE) IN HIGH TEMPERATURE AND HIGH PRESSURE WATER.

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ABSTRACT

Epoxy resins have been widely used for the manufacture of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP). It is well known that thermosetting resins are difficult to be fractionated into elemental components. Many recycling methods using subcritical and supercritical water have been developed since 2000s. However, most of studies focused on the optimization of the process parameters. Very few studies until now were focused on the study of the kinetics of the hydrolysis of epoxy resins. There are a lot of studies dealing with solid-state kinetics. Some commonly used models in this field have been applied to the hydrolysis of the CFRE. Hydrolysis experiments are performed in order to determine the evolution of the resin decomposition with time and temperature. We then use two-independent variable and one-independent variable methods to determine the kinetic parameters and to propose a global kinetic model of the hydrolysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have raised a strong interest in recent years because they offer the opportunity to design increasingly lighter and more resistant structures, more resistant. However, this growth generates a significant amount of waste. The recent European directives, as well as economic and environmental constraints have motivated the composite industry to develop recycling methods for composite wastes. The mechanical method is less suitable for the recovery of the composite material to carbon fibers as the mechanical properties are significantly deteriorated. Furthermore, the significant reduction in the size of the fibers greatly reduces the economic value thereof. The fluidized bed process is also showing a large distribution of fiber size. While recycled fibers are clean, the surface has a fluffy appearance. The processes of solvolysis and pyrolysis present the most interesting results from the point of view of the mechanical properties of recycled fibers. Pyrolysis is more suitable for energy recovery, while the solvolysis is suitable for material recovery. Indeed, the solvolysis can not only keep very good mechanical properties, but also to keep the size of the fiber, which is important for the recovery of recycled fibers. However, conventional solvolysis (low temperature) may require the use of solvents hazardous to the environment. The high temperature solvolysis was developed, allowing not only the use of less hazardous solvents, but also reducing the process time.

This paper presents the findings of an investigation into carbon fiber epoxy composites recycling, using high temperature and high pressure water. Two-independent variable (2-IV) method and one-independent variable (1-IV) method have been used in order to study the decomposition kinetics.

2 BACKGROUND

Many studies can be found in the literature on the solid-state kinetic. But very few of these studies are about the degradation kinetic of epoxy resins by the solvolysis process. Pinero-Hernanz et al [1] have studied the hydrolysis kinetic of a pre-preg CFRE (Carbon Fiber Reinforce Epoxy) between 260°C and 300°C. The pre-exponential factor and the activation energy were respectively $24.398 \times 10^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and 35.5 kJ mol^{-1} . Yuyan Liu et al [2] studied the hydrolysis of an epoxy resin between 260°C and 300°C and found an activation energy of $123.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. El Ghazzaoui [3] studied the hydrolysis of two CFREs. One was treated between 310°C and 340°C and the analysis of the results shows a pre-exponential factor of $14.4 \times 10^{75} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and an activation energy of $868.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The other was treated between 340°C and 360°C. The pre-exponential factor and the activation energy were respectively $26.6 \times 10^{39} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $507.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. A more recent study by Gong et al [4] investigated the kinetics of DDS-cured DGEBA epoxy resin in hot water between at temperatures 300°C to 330°C. The results showed that the calculated activation energy (E_a) $170.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

3 MATERIAL AND METHODS

Carbon fiber composite material

The carbon fiber material used for this study was an epoxy-amine cured and a multidirectional material. Waste off-cuts of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin were used. Distilled water from Labogros-Grosseron was used as solvent without further treatment.

Water batch reactor

The experiments were performed in a small batch reactor of about 20 mL, made up of a Swagelok connector SS-16-VCR-6-DM and two Swagelok caps SS-16-VCR-CP. One of the two caps was instrumented with one K-Type thermocouples. This enabled the measurement of the temperature in the liquid phase. Once loaded with water and a composite sample, and closed, the reactor was immersed in a salt bath of sodium nitrate and potassium nitrate mixture. The regulation was made using the temperature of the bath, allowing the temperature inside the reactor at $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The different temperatures were acquired using an Agilent unit 34970A with an acquisition card 34902A. At the end of the hydrolysis treatment, the reactor caps are first cooled by spraying cold water on the upper lid of the reactor, and then the reactor was cooled in a bath of cold water. The cooling water jet allows the cover contracts on the body of the reactor, thus avoiding the infiltration of water, which would be due to a larger contraction of the connector from the cover, when the reactor is immersed in the cold water bath.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A design of experiments (DoE) approach was used to study the influence of the operating conditions on the recycling efficiency (i.e. the yield of eliminated resin). Temperature, solvent volume, reaction time and feedstock ratio were selected as controlled variables. Pressure could not be considered as an independent variable since it is determined by the reactor temperature, the initial volume of solvent and also the initial mass of composite placed into the batch reactor.

The DoE table was built with four controlled factors and one response variable (resin degradation yield) as shown in Table 1. Two of the controlled factors (solvent volume and feedstock ratio) were maintained constant.

Experimental factors		
	Type	Levels/settings
Temperature (°C)	Multi-level	320 - 360
V_{H2O}/V_{reactor} (%v)	Quantitative	50
reaction time (s)	Quantitative	300-7200
mcomp/mH2O (%wt)	Quantitative	23

Table 1: Experimental factors and variables of the DoE.

Statistical analysis of the results was performed using commercial software called Origin9.

Figure 1 is obtained by plotting experimental results obtained for parameters in Table 1. It can be seen that the shape of the evolution of the fractional extent (α) depends on the temperature. In fact, for lower temperatures, we can observe a s-curve. This shape disappears gradually as the temperature increase.

$$\alpha = \frac{m_i - m_f}{m_i} \quad (1)$$

Where m_i and m_f are respectively the initial and final mass of resin.

Figure 1: Fractional extend of the degradation of epoxy resin for different temperatures.

Nonstationary model of the decomposition process

The degradation process of the resin occurs at the surface of the resin that reinforces the carbon fibers. Due to the low thickness of the resin coating, it can be assumed that the kinetics of the surface reaction is proportional to the weight of the remaining resin over the carbon fiber. From a phenomenological point of view the process has two main steps, first, mass transfer from the bulk

fluid to the surface and vice versa and second, the surface reaction. This implies that the estimated rate of reaction must consider both steps and it will be an effective rate of reaction[1].

The rate equations that have found application in solid-state kinetic analyse may be generalised in their derivative forms as:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = kf(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

Where t is the time or reaction and α is the fractional extent of reaction

The corresponding integrated form is as:

$$g(\alpha) = kt + c \quad (3)$$

Where c is a constant.

The commonly used expression that have been successfully used in kinetic analyses of many solid phase decomposition reactions have been summarized in Table 2.

Model		Symbol	$g(\alpha)$
Avrami-Erofeev	A2	$2(1-\alpha)[-ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$	$[-ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$
Avrami-Erofeev	A3	$3(1-\alpha)[-ln(1-\alpha)]^{2/3}$	$[-ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/3}$
Avrami-Erofeev	A4	$4(1-\alpha)[-ln(1-\alpha)]^{3/4}$	$[-ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/4}$
Prout-Tompkins	B1	$\alpha(1-\alpha)$	$ln[\alpha/((1-\alpha))]$
Manpel power law	P1	$n\alpha^{1-1/n}$	$\alpha^{1/n}$
Exponential law	E1	α	$ln\alpha$
Two-dimensional phase boundary	R2	$2(1-\alpha)^{1/2}$	$1-(1-\alpha)^{1/2}$
Three-dimensional phase boundary	R3	$3(1-\alpha)^{2/3}$	$1-(1-\alpha)^{1/3}$
One-dimensional diffusion	D1	$(1/2)\alpha$	α^2
Two-dimensional diffusion	D2	$[-ln(1-\alpha)]^{-1}$	$\alpha + (1-\alpha)ln(1-\alpha)$
Three-dimensional diffusion (Jander equation)	D3	$(3/2)(1-\alpha)^{2/3}[1-(1-\alpha)^{-1/3}]^{-1}$	$[1-(1-\alpha)^{1/3}]^2$
Three-dimensional diffusion (Ginstling-Brounshtein)	D4	$(3/2)[(1-\alpha)^{-1/3}-1]^{-1}$	$(1-2\alpha/3)-(1-\alpha)^{2/3}$
First order	F1	$(1-\alpha)$	$-ln(1-\alpha)$
Second order	F2	$(1-\alpha)^2$	$(1-\alpha)^{-1}$
Third order	F3	$(1/2)(1-\alpha)^3$	$(1-\alpha)^{-2}$

Table 2: Commonly used solid-state kinetic models[5].

The expressions in grouped according to the shape of the α -time curves as acceleratory, sigmoid or deceleratory. The deceleratory group is further subdivided according to the controlling factor assumed in the derivation, as geometric, diffusion or reaction order[5]. The expressions of Table 2, as well as several others less frequently encountered, can be represented by the general relation of Sestak and Berggren[6]:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k\alpha^n(1-\alpha)^m[-ln(1-\alpha)]^p \quad (4)$$

Where n , m , and p are natural whole numbers

We considered that the rate constant follows the Arrhenius law:

$$k = k_0 e^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}} \quad (5)$$

Where k_0 (s⁻¹) is the pre-exponential factor and E_a (J/mol) is the activation energy, R (J/mol/K) is the ideal gas constant and T (K) is the temperature.

Each model in Table 2 has been used in order to determine which of the available rate expressions provides the most acceptable fit to the experimental data. The Avrami-Erofeev model A3, which is a third order kinetic model, gives the best results.

Figure 2 shows the results of the adjustment, with a non-linear regression of equation 6, by the method of Marquardt between the fractional extent α and the two independent variables, temperature (T) and time (t). It can be seen that there is a significant difference between the experimental results and the prediction of the AE3 model. This observation is confirmed by a poor R-square of 92 %. The model suggests an activation energy equal to 246 kJ mol⁻¹K⁻¹, a pre-exponential factor of 1.38x10¹⁸ s⁻¹.

$$\alpha = 1 - \exp(-k_0 t e^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}})^3 \quad (6)$$

Figure 2: result of the non-linear regression for two independent variables

In order to improve the fit of the model, the kinetics of degradation was also studied for one independent variable (t). Figures 3 show the results of the non-linear adjustment of equation 7 for different temperatures used. Table 3 report the values of the reaction rate constant and the order of reaction for each temperature.

$$\alpha = 1 - \exp(-kt)^3 \quad (7)$$

Figure 3: result of the non-linear regression for temperature 320 °C, 330°C, 340°C, 350°C and 360°C.

Temperature (°C)	K(s ⁻¹)
320	3.1 x 10 ⁻⁴
330	5.2 x 10 ⁻⁴
340	12.6 x 10 ⁻⁴
350	33.3 x 10 ⁻⁴
360	146.3 x 10 ⁻⁴

Table 3: reaction rate constant and reaction order for different temperatures.

The temperature variation of the appropriate rate coefficient, k , is used to calculate an activation energy, E , a parameter which has frequently been identified (by analogy with the accepted interpretation for homogeneous reactions) with the energy barrier to reaction.

The Arrhenius equation in logarithmic form has been used:

$$\ln(k) = \ln(k_0) + \frac{-E_a}{R} * \frac{1}{T} \quad (8)$$

Figure 4 represents the change in the natural logarithm of the 1-IV and the 2-IV reaction rate constant as a function of the inverse of the temperature. The slope of the line resulting from the linear regression of 1-IV gives us the energy of activation and the ordinate at the origin gives us the pre-exponential factor. Analysis of these results gives a pre-exponential factor $9.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and activation energy $265 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Figure 4: Linear correlation of the reaction rate coefficient as function of temperature ($\ln(k(T))$ vs. $1/T$)

Comparing results obtained for two-independent variables and one-independent variable, it can be seen that the 2-IV curve shows a significant difference with the linear regression of the 1-IV curve. The activation energy and pre-exponential factor of both cases are very close. Comparing our results in term of activation energy with those of previous work (refer to part 2: Background), it can be seen that our activation energies are close to those of Yuyan Liu et al[2], El Ghazzaoui[3] and Gong et al[4]. However, there is an order of magnitude of difference between our results and those of Pinero-Hernanz et al [1]. This difference can be due to the fact that Pinero-Hernanz et al have used a pre-preg CFRE.

5 CONCLUSION

CFRE was proved to be successfully decomposed in high pressure and high temperature water. The yield of decomposition depends upon on temperature and time. In lower temperature, the evolution of the yield of decomposition shows a s-curve that disappear in higher temperature. The third order Avrami-Erofeev model proved to be the best to fit our experimental results. Applying this model to the two-independent variables and the one-independent variable methods, we found that the two-independent variable method shows significant difference with the one-independent variable method. Our results in term of activation energy are close those found in the literature. In most studies, the kinetics of the hydrolysis process is investigated using a mass kinetic method. Another approached mentioned, but not developed by El Ghazzaoui[3] is to considered the hydrolysis process as a combination of three different processes: chemical reaction, mass transfer and heat transfer. Then

three kinetic studies must be performed in different ways in this case. A detailed understanding of the overall kinetics results from the combination of these three studies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Piñero-Hernanz, C. Dodds, J. Hyde, J. García-Serna, M. Poliakoff, E. Lester, M. J. Cocero, S. Kingman, S. Pickering, and K. H. Wong, Chemical recycling of carbon fibre reinforced composites in nearcritical and supercritical water, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 39, no. 3, 2008, pp. 454–461.
- [2] Y. Y. Liu, H. Wei, S. Wu, and Z. Guo, Kinetic Study of Epoxy Resin Decomposition in Near-Critical Water, *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 35, no. 4, 2008, pp. 713–719.
- [3] H. El Ghazzaoui, Contribution à l'étude de la dégradation des composites carbone/époxy par solvolysse dans l'eau subcritique et supercritique en vue de leur recyclage, PhD Thesis, Université de Nantes, 2012.
- [4] X. Gong, H. Kang, Y. Liu, and S. Wu, Decomposition mechanisms and kinetics of amine/anhydride-cured DGEBA epoxy resin in near-critical water, *RSC Adv.*, vol. 5, no. 50, 2015, pp. 40269–40282.
- [5] M. E. Brown and A. K. Galwey, The distinguishability of selected kinetic models for isothermal solid-state reactions, *Thermochimica Acta*, vol. 29, no. 1, 1979, pp. 129–146.
- [6] J. Sestak and G. Berggren, Differential thermal analysis II. Application to enthalpic and kinetic measurements, *Thermochimica Acta*, vol. 3, pp. 1–12.